

THE CHALLENGES OF EXPRESSING LACUNA IN THE SECOND LANGUAGE

Alimova Maftuna Ravshanbek kizi

Teacher of Andijan State Institute of foreign languages

Abstract. *This article is dedicated to the description of the concept of "lacuna," which is a common issue in language and culture. Lacunae can be associated with a range of language issues. The first issue pertains to accurately conveying the meaning of lacunae and effectively translating them. The second issue involves difficulties in aligning concepts from the second language with one another. Furthermore, it explores the problems and solutions that arise when expressing lacunas in two languages. To find solutions to such problems, the ideas of many knowledgeable scholars have been utilized.*

Keywords: *lacuna, lacunar collocation, motivated and unmotivated, reality, socio-linguistic, theory of intercultural communication, cultural studies, thematic standpoint.*

The extensive study of the concept of lacuna has accelerated its identification as a separate linguistic category, distinguishing it from related phenomena. Initially, if all synonymous words were evaluated as lacunas, in subsequent years, the semantic range of the term "lacuna" was refined and specified. During this process, the nature of the lacuna concept became more precise and easily understandable up to a certain degree.

When comparing two or more languages, we encounter various types of lacunas within different language families. Therefore, in the classification of lacunas, it is necessary to separate lacunas within a single language and lacunas found in different language families. This idea is also affirmed by Sh.Abdurazoqova when discussing the challenges of expressing lacunas in a second language. Considering the factors and aspects mentioned, we propose the following classification of lacunas and lacunar collocations:

Surface-level: phonetic, lexical, morphemic, morphological, and syntactic lacunar collocations and lacunas.

Motivated and unmotivated lacunas. The emergence of motivated lacunas is due to the absence of a specific reality in the daily life of the language community to which the language belongs (the absence of the reality leads to its absence in the language).

Unmotivated lacunar collocations and lacunas arise without direct reference to specific realities in the life of the language community they belong to (realities exist, but are not linguistically expressed).

The discussion of unmotivated lacunas is also present in ancient Greek linguistics. In turn, motivated and unmotivated types of lacunar collocations and lacunas are further categorized as follows:

a) Ethnographic lacunar collocations and lacunas reflect the unique characteristics of daily life specific to the community associated with one of the compared languages. As an example of ethnographic lacunas in the comparison of Russian and Evenki languages, O.B. Pilayeva presents examples related to the Evenki reindeer culture (ulumi – reindeer antler, udyami – catching a wild animal), and examples related to contemporary life (onomi – going to search for mushrooms, mavutlami – catching fish with a net).

b) Linguistic-cultural and socio-historical lacunar collocations and lacunas reflect the culture, history, and social context of the community associated with one of the compared languages.

c) Mental and associative lacunar collocations and lacunas represent the understanding of the world, self-perception, thinking style, associations, and similar aspects of the community associated with one of the compared languages.

This classification takes into account different dimensions of lacunas and lacunar collocations, including surface-level linguistic aspects, cultural and historical aspects, as well as cognitive and associative

aspects. Expressing the definitive meaning of lacunae can pose challenges for translators and linguists. This complicates straightforward translation in cases where quick and simple translation indicators are absent during translation and interpretation processes.

The main reasons for challenges related to lacunae include:

Absence of words or expressions in the translator's primary language.

Concepts or objects that exist in the second language but lack corresponding equivalents in the translator's language.

Differences in the meaning or expression of words that exist in both languages.

Stylistic or cultural words in the source language that are not present in the translator's primary language.

The need for contextual or historical information to understand lacunae in the translator's primary language.

There can be various approaches to expressing lacunae, for example:

Acquiring information about the translator's proficient countries, literatures, or figures to understand words that are unfamiliar due to translation context.

Seeking consultations among translators to understand words that are absent in translation.

Learning the proficient words of the translator's primary language to understand issues in translation related to the primary language.

Challenges in expressing lacunae are encountered in the field of translation and linguistics. To resolve these challenges, translators and linguists need to establish communication and exchanges, as well as analyze language structure, historical works, content, and context.

D.R. Djumayeva also classifies lacunas and lacunar collocations from a thematic standpoint, categorizing them into the following groups:

Household and Everyday Objects: Names of rooms, household items, everyday activities.

Numismatic Lexicon: Terms related to coins, currency, and monetary systems.

Art World: Terms related to various forms of art, artistic techniques, artistic movements, and artistic expressions.

Craftsmanship: Terms related to different crafts, artisanal skills, and trades.

Mentality-related Names: Names associated with cultural mindset, values, beliefs, and attitudes.

Religious Field: Terms related to religious practices, rituals, and concepts.

Natural Zones and Phenomena: Names of natural landscapes, geographical features, and natural phenomena.

Months, Festivals, and Celebrations: Names of months, holidays, and festive occasions.

Cuisines and Dishes: Names of food and culinary traditions.

Flora and Fauna: Names of plants and animals.

Anthroponyms: Names of people, personal names.

Toponyms: Place names, names of cities, regions, and geographical locations.

This thematic classification provides a comprehensive overview of lacunas and lacunar collocations in various domains, ranging from everyday objects to cultural, artistic, religious, natural, and social aspects.

In the given article, various types of gapped expressions are classified based on their specific characteristics in one of the analyzed languages. For example:

Related to location: in English, the gapped expression "railbird" (a spectator standing on a fence during a horse race) corresponds to a gap (0) in Uzbek; the Uzbek gapped expression "taxmon" (a special place where household items are stored on top of a chest or cupboard) corresponds to a gap (0) in English; the Uzbek gapped expression "chimildiq" (the first night after a wedding when the bride sleeps with the groom

and others sleep separately, and a white sheet is hung over the bed for the proof of virginity) corresponds to a gap (0) in English.

Related to shape: in English, the gapped expression "fiddle-back" (a stool shaped like a violin) corresponds to a gap (0) in Uzbek.

Related to measurement: in Russian, the gapped expression "дюжина" (a dozen, 12 items) corresponds to a gap (0) in Uzbek; the Uzbek gapped expression "tosh" (a unit of length, approximately equal to 8 spans) corresponds to a gap (0) in Russian.

Related to time: in English, the gapped expression "time-lag" (the time interval between two related events or situations, such as the interval between lightning and thunder) corresponds to a gap (0) in Uzbek; the Uzbek gapped expression "chilla" (1. The coldest forty days of the year, 2. The period of forty days after the birth or circumcision of a child or the marriage of a girl) corresponds to a gap (0) in English.

Related to purpose: in English, the gapped expression "baby-farm" (a family that takes in babies for money) corresponds to a gap (0) in Uzbek; the Uzbek gapped expression "hashar" (the voluntary participation and support of many people in carrying out a specific task, arbitrary contribution) corresponds to a gap (0) in English.

Related to social grouping: in Uzbek, the gapped expressions "said," "tora," "taqsir," "xon," "oqsuyak" correspond to gaps (0) in English; in Russian, the gapped expressions "герцог," "князь," "граф," "боярин" correspond to gaps (0) in Uzbek.

Based on composition: in Uzbek, the gapped expression "qazi" (a food product made from the fat and meat of the sheep's tail, prepared by boiling and rendered into a solid form) corresponds to a gap (0) in Russian; the Uzbek gapped expression "sumalak" (a dish made from sprouted wheat, flour, and yogurt) corresponds to a gap (0) in Russian.

Summary:

When analyzing specific lexical systems, it is possible to identify numerous gaps. However, determining which ones should be filled requires the consensus of two lexical systems. In such processes, it is necessary to pay attention to both the distinct and shared aspects of comparative units in linguistic research. It should be emphasized that distinguishing and describing gaps from corresponding phenomena is an ongoing task in linguistics.

The authors argue that generalizing and specifying tendencies can often align in many cases, while gapping can be attributed to specific manifestations such as shape, location, time, value, and movement.

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